

Effect of Jet Diameter on Surface Quenching at Different Spatial Locations

Authors : C. Agrawal, R. Kumar, A. Gupta, B. Chatterjee

Abstract : An experimental investigation has been carried out to study the cooling of a hot horizontal Stainless Steel surface of 3 mm thickness, which has 800 ± 10 °C initial temperature. A round water jet of 22 ± 1 °C temperature was injected over the hot surface through straight tube type nozzles of 2.5-4.8 mm diameter and 250 mm length. The experiments were performed for the jet exit to target surface spacing of 4 times of jet diameter and jet Reynolds number of 5000-24000. The effect of change in jet Reynolds number on the surface quenching has been investigated from the stagnation point to 16 mm spatial location.

Keywords : hot-surface, jet impingement, quenching, stagnation point

Conference Title : ICAME 2014 : International Conference on Automotive and Mechanical Engineering

Conference Location : Zurich, Switzerland

Conference Dates : January 14-15, 2014